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New Approach for Protection of Chickens against Mycoplasma Gallisepticum and Avian Influenza H9 Disease Using a Nano-Oil Adjuvanted Combined Inactivated Vaccine

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Abstract

Mycoplasma gallisepticum is the main agent of chronic respiratory disease and also it helps greatly co-infection with low pathogenic avian Influenza (H9N2) in chickens. The protective efficacy of a combined inactivated vaccine, formulated with a locally prepared low-pathogenic avian influenza (LPAI) subtype H9N2 and *Mycoplasma gallisepticum* (MG), was evaluated in specific pathogen-free (SPF) chickens using nasal and subcutaneous routes. The prepared combined vaccine exhibited no adverse local or systemic reactions and was free from bacterial or fungal contamination. The immune response to LPAI H9N2 and MG was assessed using the hemagglutination inhibition (HI) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) tests. The results demonstrated that the vaccine induced a high level of seroconversion via both routes, beginning after the 2nd WPV and reaching peak at the 4th and 5th WPV. Antibody titers in chickens vaccinated via the subcutaneous (SC) route showed a stronger immune response compared to those vaccinated via the intranasal (IN) route. The mean reduction of viral shedding titers of LPAI H9N2 was done in SPF Embryonated chicken eggs (ECE) and it was found that 2.35 and 2 log₁₀ EID₅₀, using SC and IN routes respectively. Additionally, the challenged chicken groups against virulent MG strain after 4th WPV exhibited satisfactory protection, with protection rates of 90% and 80% for both routes, respectively. In conclusion, immunization with the inactivated combined vaccine adjuvanted with Montanide™ IMS 1313 N VG PR induced early and strong seroconversion, providing satisfactory protection compared to the control group. Adaptive immunity elicited via the SC route resulted in a higher immune response and stronger protection compared to the mucosal immunity induced via the IN route. The prepared vaccine is considered a promising vaccine when used to achieve protection against both MG and H9N2. **Key Words:** Low Pathogenic Avian Influenza (H9N2), *Mycoplasma gallisepticum*, Inactivated combined vaccine, Nano-oil emulsion.

Introduction

The poultry industry in Egypt faces several challenges that threaten its growth and sustainability. The emergence of bacterial and viral pathogens has become a major concern, leading to high morbidity and mortality rates. Low-pathogenic avian influenza (LPAI) subtype H9N2 and *Mycoplasma gallisepticum* (MG) are considered immunosuppressive diseases, playing a crucial role in predisposing poultry to secondary bacterial and viral infections.

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H9N2 is a widespread respiratory disease in chickens caused by Influenza A viruses, belonging to the family *Orthomyxoviridae*. LPAI infections often present with minimal clinical signs, such as anorexia, reduced water intake, depression, coughing, sneezing, and dyspnea (Matrosovich et al., 2001). In Egypt, LPAI H9N2 of the G1 lineage was first reported in 2011 (El-Zoghby et al., 2012). Since then, the virus has become endemic and continues to circulate, causing recurrent outbreaks. Affected flocks experience mortality rates ranging from 10% to 65% within 5–7 days of clinical symptom onset, with increased mortality in cases of co-infection with other respiratory pathogens.

Avian mycoplasmosis is caused by several pathogenic *Mycoplasma* species, among which *Mycoplasma gallisepticum* (MG) and *M. synoviae* (MS) are the most significant. MG is responsible for chronic respiratory disease in domestic poultry, particularly when flocks are exposed to stress or other respiratory pathogens. Clinical signs of MG infection range from subclinical manifestations to severe respiratory symptoms, including coryza, conjunctivitis, coughing, sneezing, nasal exudate, rales, and open-beak breathing (WOAH, 2024).

To date, vaccination remains the most effective strategy for enhancing immune responses in chickens, mitigating the effects of emerging infectious diseases, and providing resistance against challenging pathogens (Adams, 2019). Various vaccine types, including inactivated, subunit, DNA-based, and live attenuated vaccines, have been developed and shown to offer significant protection. The use of combined inactivated vaccines presents several advantages, such as providing immunity against multiple diseases simultaneously, enhancing immune responses, reducing vaccination costs, and minimizing the stress associated with multiple vaccination shots.

In recent years, modern adjuvants such as the Montanide™ ISA series have gained increasing attention due to their safety and efficacy in veterinary vaccines. Montanide™ IMS 1313 N VG PR, an aqueous-based nanoparticle adjuvant, has demonstrated superior immune-stimulating activity in veterinary vaccines. This adjuvant is suitable for both oral and parenteral vaccination, enhancing immune protection across various animal species (Jang SI et al., 2011).

Therefore, the present study aimed to develop an inactivated combined vaccine using inactivated cultures of LPAI H9N2 and MG adjuvanted with Montanide™ ISA 1313. The vaccine was administered via subcutaneous and intranasal routes, and its efficacy was evaluated in specific pathogen-free (SPF) chickens.

Materials and Methods

SPF Chickens

A total of 154 one-day-old specific pathogen-free (SPF) chicks were obtained from the National Project for the Production of SPF Eggs, Kom Oshim, Fayoum, Egypt. All birds were housed in biosafety isolators. Twelve chicks were used to confirm the completion of inactivation, another twelve for safety testing, and the remaining 130 for potency testing.

Strains

Mycoplasma gallisepticum (MG)

A locally isolated and well-characterized MG strain was obtained from the Central Laboratory for Evaluation of Veterinary Biologics (CLEVB) reference bank, Cairo, Egypt, under accession number ATCC10522.

Low-Pathogenic Avian Influenza (LPAI) H9N2

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A local LPAI (H9N2) isolate was supplied by the CLEVB Reference Strain Bank which originally obtained from Animal Health Research Institute (AHRI). This strain was submitted to the Gene Bank as A/chicken/Egypt/V3506/2020 under accession number MW600497 with a titer of $8 \log_{10} \text{EID}_{50} / \text{ml}$ and $8 \log_{2} \text{HI}$ titer.

Adjuvant

Montanide™ IMS 1313 N VG PR (SEPPIC, France) was used as an adjuvant in the formulation of the combined vaccine by mixing equal volume with the antigenic phase with 1:1 ratio as per the manufacturer's recommendations.

Vaccine preparation

Preparation of *Mycoplasma gallisepticum* antigenic phase

The selected seed culture of *M. gallisepticum* was inoculated into a starter culture flask 250 ml of Frey's medium. Fresh medium was inoculated with a 24 hours broth culture equivalent to 10% of the volume of medium used. The Mycoplasma cells were harvested and washed by centrifugation at 12,000 XG for 30 minutes after 48-hour incubation at 37°C in carbon dioxide incubator. After washings, a final suspension of antigen was prepared to contain 1% packed cell volume in phosphate-buffer saline in final product.

Preparation of H9N2 antigenic phase

The H9N2 virus seed was propagated and titrated in 9-11 days old SPF ECE. Allantoic fluid was collected and slide HA test was performed. The obtained titer was $10^{10} \text{ED}_{50} / \text{ml}$ before inactivation.

Inactivation of Virus and Bacteria

Both LPAI (H9N2) and MG suspensions were inactivated overnight using formalin at a final concentration of 0.1 and 0.3% of the total volume respectively (WOAH, 2024, Gomaa et al., 2019 and El-Naggar et al., 2022). To confirm the complete inactivation of the virus and bacteria, each suspension was inoculated in five SPF chickens while two SPF chickens were maintained as controls. If the inoculated chickens exhibited no clinical signs or mortality, the inactivated suspensions were considered safe for emulsification with the vaccine adjuvant (Abido et al., 2020).

Preparation of the combined inactivated MG and H9N2 vaccine.

Equal volumes of inactivated LPAI (H9N2) and MG suspensions were mixed and emulsified with Montanide™ IMS 1313 N VG PR with a ratio of 1:1 according to the manufacturer's recommendations. The final vaccine dose was adjusted to contain $10^8 \text{ HA units/dose}$ of LPAI (H9N2) and $1 \times 10^8 \text{ CFU/dose}$ of MG that calculated using Rodwell and Whitcomb's 1983, Bekele and Assefa 2018, Gomaa et al., 2019 and WOAH 2024

Evaluation of the prepared vaccine

The prepared vaccines were tested for sterility, safety, and purity following the guidelines of the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH, 2024).

Purity test

The test was done before preparation of vaccine. The MG and H9N2 cultures were tested for purity by the cultivation into nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Sterility Test

The sterility test was performed to ensure the vaccine was free from bacterial, fungal, and mycoplasma contamination.

Safety Test

Ten seronegative SPF chickens were inoculated with a **double dose** of the prepared inactivated vaccine via the **subcutaneous (SC) and intranasal (IN) routes** (5 SPF chickens per route). Two control SPF chickens were maintained throughout the experiment. Vaccinated birds were observed for **21 days** for any local or systemic adverse reactions.

Potency test

Experimental Design:

A total of **130 SPF chicks** were divided into three groups. **Group 1 (50 chicks)** was vaccinated with the combined vaccine via **subcutaneous route (SC)**, **Group 2(50 chicks)** was vaccinated with the combined vaccine via **intranasal route (IN)**, and **Group 3 (30 chicks)** was kept as an non-vaccinated **control group**.

Blood sample collection

Random blood samples were collected weekly until the **8th week post-vaccination** for evaluation of **humoral immune response of the prepared combined vaccine**. Collected sera were tested for **H9N2 and MG antibodies** using **HI and ELISA tests**, respectively.

Hemagglutination Inhibition (HI) Test:

The HI test was performed to estimate specific LPAI (H9N2) antibody levels in vaccinated SPF chickens using **4 HAU** of LPAI (H9N2), according to **WOAH (2024)** guidelines.

ELISA Test:

The immune response to MG was evaluated using the Mycoplasma Gallisepticum (MG) Antibody Test Kit (BioChek, Cat. No. CK114). The test was performed following the manufacturer's instructions. Antibody titers ≥ 668 were considered positive, while titers < 668 were deemed negative.

Challenge Test (WOAH 2024)

Ten SPF chickens from each vaccinated group (Group 1,2), along with 5 control chickens (Group3) were challenged nasally with **0.1 ml** containing **6 log₁₀ EID₅₀** of the LPAI (H9N2) strain at the **4th WPV**. Chickens were monitored for **14 days post-challenge** for clinical signs and mortality. Oropharyngeal swabs were collected on the **3rd and 7th days post-challenge** to assess viral shedding via titration in SPF embryonated chicken eggs (ECE).

Similarly, the chickens were challenged via abdominal air sac inoculation with **10⁶ CFU/ml** of a virulent MG strain. The chickens were monitored daily for **14 days post-challenge**, and all succumbed birds were examined for **air sacculitis gross lesions**. Survivors were euthanized, and their lesions were scored as follows:

Lesion Scoring System: **0** = No lesions, **1** = Slight cloudiness and thickening of membranes with fibrinous exudates, **2** = Moderate cloudiness and thickening of membranes with fibrinous exudates, **3** = Severe

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cloudiness and thickening of membranes with fibrinous exudates, 4 = Extensive thickening with fibrinous and caseous exudates. The **mean air sacculitis lesion scores** were used to calculate the **protection percentage** as follows:

Protection % = Mean score of air sacculitis gross lesions in challenged control group – in challenged vaccinated group x 100 / Mean score of air sacculitis gross lesions in challenged control group. The test is not valid unless the challenged control group is recorded a mean air sacculitis gross lesions score of at least 3 meanwhile the vaccine is potent if obtained protection percentage is not less than 70%.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of the obtained data was performed using SPSS software, version 21 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA, 2012). A t-test was employed to compare the means between the vaccinated groups and assess the significance of differences in terms of humoral immune response in the outcomes of interest. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Results were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to interpret the magnitude of the effects.

Ethical Consideration

The project was approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (ARC-IACUC) of the Agricultural Research Center, under the approval code ARCCLEVB 109-24.

Results

Assessment of Virus and Bacteria Inactivation

All SPF chickens injected with the inactivated virus and bacteria remained alive without exhibiting any clinical signs, confirming complete inactivation.

Purity Test

The cultures of MG and H9N2 used in prepared vaccines were confirmed to be pure.

Sterility Test

The prepared vaccines were free from bacterial, fungal, and Mycoplasma contamination.

Safety Test

The prepared vaccines were found to be safe. No clinical symptoms were observed in SPF chickens following subcutaneous (S/C) or intranasal (I/N) inoculation with a double dose of the vaccine.

Results of Hemagglutination Inhibition (HI) Test against LPAI (H9N2) in Vaccinated chickens

As shown in **Table (1)**, the HI antibody titer in vaccinated SPF chickens increased gradually from the 1st week post-vaccination (WPV), reaching peak titers at the 4th WPV (6.2 and 5.5) for the S/C and I/N vaccination routes, respectively. The titers remained at their peak for three weeks before gradually declining by the 8th WPV (4.9 and 4.1). Statistical analysis showed a p-value of 0.000 between the different routes, indicating a statistically significant difference

Table 1. Antibody titers against H9N2 in the sera of vaccinated chickens as determined by HI test.

Week Post Vaccination	S/C inoculated chickens (Gp1)	I/N inoculated chickens (Gp2)
Pre	0	0
1 W	2.5	1.5

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2 W	4.5	4
3 W	5.5	4.8
4 W	6.2	5.5
5 W	6.1	5.3
6 W	6.1	5
7 W	5.9	4.8
8 W	4.9	4.1

Results of ELISA test against MG in Vaccinated chickens

The immune response in vaccinated chickens was monitored until the 8th WPV using ELISA. The antibody titers in the S/C vaccinated group were consistently higher than those in the I/N vaccinated group. As shown in Table 2, the titers increased gradually, peaking at the 4th WPV (5733 and 4492 for S/C and I/N, respectively) before declining, though remaining positive. Statistical analysis showed a p-value of 0.001 between the different routes, indicating a statistically significant difference.

Table 2. Antibody titers against MG in the sera of vaccinated chickens as determined by ELISA test.

Week post vaccination	S/C inoculated chickens (Gp1)	I/N inoculated chickens (Gp2)
Pre	0	0
1W	1331	1109
2 W	1843	1664
3 W	3673	3125
4 W	5733	4492
5 W	5200	4210
6 W	4827	4026
7 W	4708	3892
8 W	4114	3308

Result of challenge test against LPAI (H9N2):

No clinical signs or mortality were observed in any of the challenged chickens. As shown in **Table (3)**, viral shedding, measured in SPF embryonated chicken eggs (ECE), was higher at the 3rd day post-challenge (DPC) compared to the 7th DPC in all groups. However, the reduction in viral shedding was greater in the S/C vaccinated group (2.35 log₁₀ EID₅₀) compared to the I/N vaccinated group (2.0 log₁₀ EID₅₀).

Table 3. Mean titer in reduction of viral shedding

Chicken groups	3 rd DPC	7 th DPC	Mean viral shedding	Reduction in viral shedding
Vaccinated S/C	3.9	2	2.95	2.35
Vaccinated I/N	4.2	2.4	3.3	2
Control	6.1	4.5	5.3	-

Result of challenge test against MG:

As shown in **Table (4)**, the S/C vaccinated group achieved a 90% protection rate, while the I/N vaccinated group showed an 80% protection rate at the 4th WPV. In contrast, the unvaccinated control group had a protection rate of only 20%.

Table 4. Protection Percentage of Vaccinated Birds Challenged with Virulent MG strain

Chicken groups	No of chickens with lesion	Protection%
Vaccinated S/C	1/10	90
Vaccinated I/N	2/10	80
Control	8/10	20%

Discussion

Vaccination is an effective tool for controlling infections caused by low pathogenic avian influenza (LPAI) H9N2 and *Mycoplasma gallisepticum* (MG) in poultry. Both pathogens significantly impact the poultry industry and contribute to secondary viral and bacterial infections. The use of a combined vaccine offers several advantages, including reduced handling stress, simplified vaccination schedules, time and labor savings, and synergistic protection against overlapping clinical syndromes.

Montanide ISA 1313 has recently been widely used in vaccine formulations for various poultry species and rabbits (Abotaleb, MM, 2024). A key question arises: why is Montanide ISA 1313 considered a high-quality adjuvant? This adjuvant enhances the immune response by ensuring a sustained release of the antigen while stimulating both humoral and cellular immunity (Dhakar and Renukaradhya, 2019). Additionally, it is compatible with a wide range of antigens, including peptides, inactivated pathogens, and proteins.

This study aimed to prepare and evaluate a combined vaccine against LPAI (H9N2) and MG using two inoculation routes: subcutaneous (S/C) and intranasal (I/N). A total of 130 SPF chickens were divided into three groups: G1 (50 SPF chickens) vaccinated via S/C, G2 (50 SPF chickens) vaccinated via I/N, and G3 (30 SPF chickens) kept as an unvaccinated control group until the end of the experiment. Blood samples were collected from all groups up to the 8th week post-vaccination (WPV), and sera were examined for antibodies against LPAI and MG using hemagglutination inhibition (HI) and ELISA tests, respectively. A challenge test was conducted at the 4th WPV for each group using pathogenic LPAI and MG strains.

The quality control of the prepared combined vaccine followed international protocols set by the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH 2024), assessing sterility, safety, and potency. The sterility test confirmed the absence of bacterial, fungal, or *Mycoplasma* contamination in the vaccine. Additionally, no clinical symptoms or adverse reactions were observed in SPF chickens that received a double dose of the inactivated bivalent vaccine, confirming its safety.

Regarding potency, the immune response against H9N2 in chickens vaccinated via both S/C and I/N routes was evaluated using the HI test. Neutralizing antibodies were detected as early as the 2nd WPV, which can be attributed to the presence of Montanide ISA 1313, known for inducing an early immune response (Abotaleb et al., 2024). The results demonstrated that both administration methods produced satisfactory antibody levels after the 2nd WPV, aligning with Singh et al. (2015), who reported that a protective HI titer for H9N2 is $\geq 4 \log_2$. The antibody levels in all vaccinated groups gradually increased from the 1st WPV, peaked at the 4th WPV, and remained at maximum levels until the 6th WPV (Ali et al., 2017; Abotaleb et al., 2019). After the 7th WPV, antibody levels began to decline, likely due to the gradual attenuation of the immune response or the waning of immune memory (Xiaopan et al., 2024). S/C inoculation route produced significantly higher levels of antibody titers than I/N route.

During the challenge test, no mortality or clinical symptoms were observed in any vaccinated or control chickens. The efficacy of the H9N2 vaccine was primarily assessed by measuring the reduction in viral shedding in oropharyngeal swabs from vaccinated and control chickens (WOAH 2024). The mean viral shedding titers for vaccinated chickens using the S/C and I/N routes were 2.35 and 2.0 \log_{10} EID₅₀,

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respectively. These results indicate that the vaccine was effective, as an efficient vaccine is expected to reduce viral shedding by $\geq 2 \log_{10}$ EID₅₀ (WOAH 2024).

Additionally, the ELISA test was used to monitor the post-vaccination immune response against MG. The results showed that a positive antibody titer was detected after the 1st WPV and gradually increased, peaking at the 4th WPV with titers of 5733 and 4492 for S/C and I/N routes, respectively. These findings align with studies by **Atalla et al. (2015)** and **Bekele and Assefa (2018)**, which reported that chickens receiving oil-based MG vaccines develop protective levels of anti-MG antibodies. **Noor et al. (2020)** also stated that oil-adjuvant MG vaccines induce anti-MG antibodies in broilers within 15 days post-vaccination. The S/C inoculation route produced significantly higher levels of antibody titers than I/N route.

A challenge test was conducted on all vaccinated and control groups using a homologous MG strain at the 4th WPV. The results demonstrated that vaccinated chickens in the S/C and I/N groups achieved protection rates of 90% and 80%, respectively. According to **WOAH (2024)**, the minimum protection threshold for vaccine batch release is 70%, indicating that the prepared vaccine met the efficacy standards.

In conclusion, the newly formulated MG + H9N2 with Montanide™ Seppic IMS 1313 as an adjuvant, was proven to be safe, sterile, well-tolerated, and highly immunogenic enhance an effective immunization strategy and promising to be a protective vaccine when used against both Mg and H9N2 pathogens.

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